

TECHNICAL, ECONOMIC, AND ALLOCATIVE EFFICIENCY OF SOYBEAN CROP IN VIDARBHA REGION OF MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract

The present study was conducted in Vidarbha region of Maharashtra with objective to study of technical, economic and allocative efficiency of soybean. This research paper was based on the secondary data collected from the Agricultural Prices and Costs Scheme, located in the Department of Agricultural Economics and Statistics, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, AKOLA for the year 2022-2023, the study revealed that the majority of farmers (72%) operating at over 90% TE, no increase is necessary, indicating they are already at or near optimal efficiency. The results revealed that a one percent increase in the prices of human labour, bullock labour, and seed decreased the profit by 1.48, 0.03, and 0.79 percent respectively. In the study revealed that the economic efficiency ranged from 0.40% to 99.90%, with a mean efficiency of 42.47%. The wide range of efficiency scores indicated significant variability in the economic performance of soybean farmers in the region. The majority of farmers (19%) fell into the lowest efficiency category of less than 10%, suggesting that a considerable portion of the sample struggled with economic efficiency in soybean production. The AE of the sampled farmers was 47.3%. This indicates that, on average, farmers could reduce input costs by 52.7% without reducing output if they were fully allocatively efficient.

Keywords: Technical, Economic, Efficiency, Vidarbha

Introduction

Agricultural output can be increased through either area expansion or productivity improvement. In the Indian context, land is a shrinking resource for agriculture owing to competing demand for its use, hence further increase in agriculture production has been achieved by increasing productivity of land. Productivity can be increased through one or its combination of its determinants -the technology, the qualities and type of resources used the efficiency with which resource are used.

If farmer has making efficient utilization of existing resources, effort designed to improve efficiency would be cost-effective then introducing new technology as means of increasing agriculture output. The soybean, or soya bean (*Glycine max*) is a species of legume native to East Asia, widely grown for its edible bean, which has numerous uses. Soybeans contain significant amounts of phytic acid, dietary minerals and B vitamins. India's total area under soybean cultivation in 2022-23 is 130.84 Lakh hectares with production 149.85 Lak tonnes and productivity is 1145 kg/hectares. The major soybean growing states are Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Karnataka, Gujarat, and Telangana. In Maharashtra area under soybean cultivation is 49.26 Lakh hectares with production 66.16 Lakh tonnes and productivity is 1343 Kg/ Hectares. (Source: Ministry of Agriculture & farmer's welfare, Govt. of India)

Material And Methods**Selection of area**

The present study was undertaken in vidarbha region of Maharashtra. The data pertains for the year 2022-23

Source of data

The study will be based on secondary data, 100 farmers for each crop will be collected from the Agricultural Prices and Costs Scheme, located in the Department of Agricultural Economics and Statistics, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, AKOLA for the year 2022-2023

Analytical tools and techniques:**Stochastic frontier approach**

In the present study stochastic production frontier function and stochastic profit frontier functions were used to determine the farm-specific allocative, technical and economic efficiencies respectively.

Stochastic production frontier function-

In the present study, the stochastic frontier approach was used to measure the farm specific efficiencies of soybean, cotton and tur cultivating farms. (Aigner et al., 1977; Kalirajan and Shand, 1889; Sharma and Datta, 1997) The stochastic frontier model is called a

'composed' model because the error term is composed of two independent elements, namely-

$$\Sigma_i = v_i - u_i \quad i = 1, \dots, n$$

The term v_i is the symmetric component and permits random variation in output due to factors like weather and plant disease. It is assumed to be identically and independently distributed $v_i \approx N(0, \sigma^2 v)$. A one-sided component ($u_i \geq 0$) reflects technical efficiency relative to stochastic frontier $Q_i = Q(Xk_i, \beta) e^{v_i}$. Thus $u_i = 0$ for any farm lying on the frontier while $u_i > 0$ for any farm lying below the frontier. Hence expression (u_i) represents the amount by which the frontier exceeds realized output. The distribution of u_i is assumed to be half-normal.

A measure of technical efficiency was first introduced by Farrell (1957) for a cross-section of firms by using a deterministic approach. He illustrated his ideas of efficiency using a simple example involving firms that use two inputs (x_1 and x_2) to produce a single output (q), under the assumption of constant returns to scale. The curve SS' in following figure represents the unit isoquant of fully efficient firms and permits the measurement of technical efficiency. If a given firm uses quantities of inputs, defined by the point P, to produce a unit of output, the technical inefficiency of that firm is represented by the distance QP, which is the amount in which all inputs could be proportionately reduced without a reduction in output. This is usually expressed in percentage terms by the ratio QP/OP, which represented the percentage in which all inputs can be optimally reduced to achieve technically efficient production. Hence, the technical efficiency (TE) of a firm can be measured by the ratio

$$TE = OQ/OP$$

Technical inefficiency is equal to $1 - OQ/OP$ and takes a value between zero and one. Hence, it provides an indicator of the degree of technical inefficiency of the firm. A value of one implies that the firm is fully technically efficient.

Specification of the model

$$\ln Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln X_1 + \beta_2 \ln X_2 + \beta_3 \ln X_3 + \beta_4 \ln X_4 + \beta_5 \ln X_5 + (V_i - U_i)$$

Where,
 Y_i = Output of specific crops(Soybean) (Quintals ha⁻¹)
 X_1 = Human labour (hrs ha⁻¹)
 X_2 = Bullock labours (hrs ha⁻¹)
 X_3 = Machine hours (hrs ha⁻¹)
 X_4 = Quantity of seeds (kg ha⁻¹)
 X_5 = Quantity of fertilizers (kg ha⁻¹)
 V_i = Random variable
 U_i = Farm specific technical efficiency related variable
 β_0 = Intercept/Constant

Stochastic profit frontier function

Stochastic frontier profit function was used to estimate economic efficiency of sample maize. (Ali and Flinn, 1989; Rahman, 2003; Galawat and Yabe, 2012). The stochastic profit frontier function was estimated as-

$$\Pi_i = f(X_i, P_i) + (v_i - u_i)$$

where,
 Π_i = Normalized profit at cost-A of the ith farmer.
 X_i = The vector of variable input prices divided by output price faced by the ith farm. P_i = The vector of fixed factor of the ith farm.
 v_i = random error due to factors outside the control of the farmers.
 u_i = A non- negative random variable associated with economic inefficiency component

The economic efficiency in relation to the stochastic profit frontier is given by,

$$EE_i = \exp(-u_i)$$

Specification of the model

$$\ln \Pi_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln X_1 + \beta_2 \ln X_2 + \beta_3 \ln X_3 + \beta_4 \ln X_4 + \beta_5 \ln X_5 + (V_i - U_i)$$

Where,
 Π_i = Normalized profit at cost-A of the ith farmer.
 X_1 = Human labour wage rate per hr normalized by output price of ith farm.

X_2 =Bullock labour wage rate per hr normalized by output price of ith farm.
 X_3 = Machine wage rate per hour normalized by output price of ith farm.
 X_4 = Price of seed per kg normalized by the output price of ith farm.
 X_5 = Price of fertilizer per kg normalized by the output price of ith farm.
 V_i = Random variable
 U_i = Farm-specific economic efficiency related variable
 β_0 = Intercept
 Factor price is obtained by dividing the price of input with the output price. Allocative efficiency was estimated by dividing economic efficiency with technical efficiency for each farm.

$$AE_i = EE_i / TE_i$$

Results And Discussion

1.1 Estimation of coefficient of stochastic frontier production function of soybean

Maximum likelihood estimate (MLE) of stochastic frontier production function along with mean technical efficiency given in below table.1
 The stochastic frontier production function analysis for soybean cultivation reveals several key insights. The study revealed that the Human labor shows a negative coefficient (-0.08407), suggesting that increased labor input lead to diminishing returns, possibly due to over-cultivation or inefficient labor allocation. Bullock labor has a minimal positive impact (0.00695), while machine hours demonstrate a negative effect (-0.04821), which could indicate potential overuse or inefficiency in mechanization. Seed input shows a slight positive influence (0.02491), and fertilizer use has a more substantial positive impact (0.06412), highlighting its importance in soybean production. The high gamma value (0.94951) suggests that technical inefficiency significantly contributes to output variability. With a mean technical efficiency of 91.61%, there is still room for improvement in production practices. The positive log-likelihood function (66.73319) indicates a good fit of the model to the data. These findings emphasize the need for optimizing labor and machine use, while underscoring the benefits of appropriate fertilizer application in soybean cultivation.

Table :1 Coefficient of stochastic frontier production function (Soybean)

	Coefficient	Standard error
Intercept	1.47206	0.24035
Human labour(Hrs/Ha)	-0.08407	0.0871
Bullock labour(Hrs/Ha)	0.00695	0.02895
Machine bours (Hrs/Ha)	-0.04821	0.06118
Seed (Kg/Ha)	0.02491	0.06047
Fertilizer(Kg/Ha)	0.06412**	0.02289
Sigma- squared(v)	0.00227	
Gamma	0.94951	
Log-likelihood function	66.73319	
Mean TE (%)	91.61	

Technical efficiency of soybean farmers

The study revealed that the majority of farmers (72%) demonstrate high efficiency, operating at over 90% TE, with an average of 97.13% in this group. This suggests that a significant portion of the sample is utilizing resources effectively. The overall mean TE of 91.61% indicates generally good production practices across the sample. However, there is notable variation, with the lowest TE at 11.50% and the highest at 97.13%. A small percentage of farmers (1%) fall below 10% TE, indicating severe inefficiencies and the potential for substantial

improvement. The middle ranges (50.01-90% TE) account for 27% of the farmers, with room for moderate improvements in resource utilization. Notably, no farmers fall within the 10.01-50% TE range, suggesting a polarization between high and low performers. The data implies that while most farmers are operating near optimal efficiency, there's still potential for improvement, particularly for the lower-performing farms. Targeted interventions and knowledge sharing from high-performing farms could help bridge this efficiency gap and increase overall soybean production in the region.

Table :2 Distribution of sample farmers under different levels of Technical efficiency (Soybean)

TE (%)	No. of Farm	Percentage to total	Average	Percentage to increase production to achieve maximum efficiency
<10	1.00	1.00	1.00	98.97
10.01-20	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
20.01-30	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
30.01-40	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
40.01-50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
50.01-60	2.00	2.00	57.40	40.90

60.01-70	2.00	2.00	68.67	29.30
70.01-80	9.00	9.00	77.16	20.56
80.01-90	14.00	14.00	86.39	11.06
>90	72.00	72.00	97.13	0.00
Mean TE(%)	91.61			
Min TE (%)	11.50			
Max TE (%)	97.13			

the percentage increase required to achieve maximum efficiency provides valuable insights into the potential for production improvement. For the majority of farmers (72%) operating at over 90% TE, no increase is necessary, indicating they are already at or near optimal efficiency. However, the remaining farmers show varying degrees of potential for improvement. The most striking case is the 1% of farmers with TE below 10%, requiring a substantial 98.97% increase in production to reach maximum efficiency. This group represents the highest potential for improvement but may also face the most significant challenges. Farmers in the 50.01-60% TE range need a 40.90% increase, while those in the 60.01-70% range require a 29.30% boost. The 9% of farmers in the 70.01-80% TE category could increase

production by 20.56%, and the 14% in the 80.01-90% range need an 11.06% improvement.

1.3 Estimation of coefficient of stochastic frontier Profit function of soybean

Maximum likelihood estimate (MLE) of stochastic frontier profit function along with mean economical efficiency given in below table 3

The study revealed that the coefficient of machine hours (0.099956) showed a significant positive effect on profits. The result indicated that a one percent increase in the price of machine hours increased the profit by approximately 0.1 percent. Similarly, fertilizer prices had a positive impact on profit, with a coefficient of 0.0261.

Table :3 Coefficient of stochastic frontier profit function (Soybean)

Variables	Coefficient	Standard error
Intercept	9.03102	0.00035
Human labour(Rs/Hrs)	-1.48248***	0.00034
Bullock labour(Rs/Hrs)	-0.03305***	0.00009
Machine bours (Rs/Hrs)	0.099956***	0.00045
Seed (Rs/Kg)	-0.7864***	0.00022
Fertilizer(Rs/Kg)	0.0261***	0.00009
Sigma- squared(v)	0.00341	
Gamma	1	
Log-likelihood function	-155.63853	
Mean EE (%)	42.47	

Conversely, the coefficients of human labour (-1.48248), bullock labour (-0.03305), and seed (-0.7864) showed significant negative effects on profits. The results demonstrated that a one percent increase in the prices of human labour, bullock labour, and seed decreased the profit by 1.48, 0.03, and 0.79 percent respectively. The log likelihood function (-155.63853) was negative, indicating potential areas for model improvement or underlying complexities in the data.

The mean economic efficiency (EE) of the sample farms was 42.47 percent, which suggested that the sample farms could potentially

increase their overall profit by 57.53 percent through more efficient resource allocation and management practices. The gamma value of 1 indicated that all of the variation in profit was due to economic inefficiency.

1.4 Economic efficiency of Soybean farmers

The frequency distribution of sample farms by the level of economic efficiency in rising the soybean crop is shown in Table 4

Table :4 Distribution of sample farmers under different levels of Economic efficiency (Soybean)

EE (%)	No. of Farm	Percentage to total	Avarage	Percentage to increase production to achieve maximum efficiency
<10	19.00	19.00	0.99	99.01
10.01-20	5.00	5.00	17.21	82.77
20.01-30	11.00	11.00	24.74	75.24
30.01-40	11.00	11.00	34.98	64.98
40.01-50	13.00	13.00	45.71	54.24
50.01-60	14.00	14.00	55.76	44.18
60.01-70	9.00	9.00	66.15	33.78
70.01-80	8.00	8.00	74.89	25.04
80.01-90	5.00	5.00	83.19	16.73
>90	5.00	5.00	99.90	0.00
Mean EE(%)	42.47			
Min EE (%)	0.40			
Max EE (%)	99.90			

In the study revealed that the economic efficiency ranged from 0.40% to 99.90%, with a mean efficiency of 42.47%. The wide range of efficiency scores indicated significant variability in the economic

performance of soybean farmers in the region. The majority of farmers (19%) fell into the lowest efficiency category of less than 10%, suggesting that a considerable portion of the sample struggled with

economic efficiency in soybean production. These least efficient farmers had the potential to increase their production by up to 99.01% to achieve the maximum efficiency level. On the other hand, only 5% of the farmers achieved an efficiency level greater than 90%, demonstrating that a small fraction of the sample was operating near optimal economic efficiency.

The distribution of farmers across different efficiency levels was relatively spread out. Approximately 46% of the farmers had an economic efficiency below 50%, indicating that nearly half of the sample had substantial room for improvement in their production practices. The remaining 54% of farmers displayed efficiency levels above 50%, with the largest concentration (14%) falling in the 50.01-60% range. Farmers in the 60.01-70% efficiency range, comprising 9% of the sample, had the potential to increase their production by 33.78% to reach maximum efficiency. Those in the 70.01-80% range (8% of the sample) could improve their production by 25.04%, while farmers in the 80.01-90% category (5% of the sample) had the potential to increase production by 16.73%.

1.5 Allocative efficiency of soybean farmers

The frequency distribution of sample farms by the level of allocative efficiency in soybean production is presented in Table 5, the distribution of sample farmers under various levels of allocative efficiency (AE) in

Table :5 Distribution of sample farmers under different levels of Allocative efficiency (Soybean)

AE (%)	No. of Farm	Percentage to total	Avarage	Percentage to increase production to achieve maximum efficiency
<10	19	19	1.16	99.59
10.01-20	3	3	18.43	93.56
20.01-30	9	9	23.12	91.92
30.01-40	12	12	34.36	88.00
40.01-50	10	10	47.09	83.55
50.01-60	15	15	55.51	80.61
60.01-70	9	9	64.59	77.44
70.01-80	8	8	73.37	74.37
80.01-90	9	9	84.71	70.41
>90	6	6	132.98	53.55
Mean AE(%)	47.3			
Min AE (%)	0.5			
Max AE (%)	286.26			

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study that the Human labor shows a negative coefficient (-0.08407), suggesting that increased labor input lead to diminishing returns, possibly due to over-cultivation or inefficient labor allocation. Bullock labor has a minimal positive impact (0.00695), while machine hours demonstrate a negative effect (-0.04821), which could indicate potential overuse or inefficiency in mechanization. Seed input shows a slight positive influence (0.02491), and fertilizer use has a more substantial positive impact (0.06412), highlighting its importance in soybean production. the majority of farmers (72%) operating at over 90% TE, no increase is necessary, indicating they are already at or near optimal efficiency. However, the remaining farmers show varying degrees of potential for improvement. The results revealed that a one percent increase in the prices of human labour, bullock labour, and seed decreased the profit by 1.48, 0.03, and 0.79 percent respectively. In the study revealed that the economic efficiency ranged from 0.40% to 99.90%, with a mean efficiency of 42.47%. The wide range of efficiency scores indicated significant variability in the economic performance of soybean farmers in the region. The majority of farmers (19%) fell into the lowest efficiency category of less than 10%, suggesting that a considerable portion of the sample struggled with economic efficiency in soybean production. the distribution of sample farmers under various levels of allocative efficiency (AE) in soybean production. The allocative efficiency percentage ranged widely among the sampled farmers, from a minimum of 0.5% to a maximum of 286.26%. On average, the AE of the sampled farmers was 47.3%. This indicates that, on average, farmers could

soybean production. The allocative efficiency percentage ranged widely among the sampled farmers, from a minimum of 0.5% to a maximum of 286.26%. On average, the AE of the sampled farmers was 47.3%. This indicates that, on average, farmers could reduce input costs by 52.7% without reducing output if they were fully allocatively efficient.

A significant proportion of the farmers (19%) fell into the lowest AE category of less than 10%, with an average efficiency of 1.16%. This group of farmers had the highest potential for improvement, as they needed to increase their production efficiency by 99.59% to achieve maximum allocative efficiency. On the other hand, 6% of the farmers achieved an AE of over 90%, with an average of 132.98%. These farmers needed to improve their production efficiency by 53.55% to reach the maximum efficiency level, which is still considerable but much lower than those in the lowest efficiency category.

The data showed a gradual decline in the percentage of farmers as the AE categories increased. Farmers in the middle efficiency range (40.01-60%) represented 25% of the sample, suggesting that a considerable number of farmers were moderately efficient but still had room for improvement. Specifically, these farmers needed to increase their efficiency by 83.55% to 80.61% to achieve maximum efficiency.

reduce input costs by 52.7% without reducing output if they were fully allocatively efficient.

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